

Adenocarcinoma of the Appendix as an Incidental Finding after Appendectomy for Suspected Acute Appendicitis

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ABSTRACT

Appendiceal adenocarcinoma is a rare neoplasm of the gastrointestinal tract, usually diagnosed incidentally after an appendectomy performed for suspected acute appendicitis. We present the case of a 58-year-old female patient who was admitted to the emergency department with colicky abdominal pain of three weeks' duration, accompanied by nausea and constipation, unresponsive to medical treatment. Abdominopelvic CT suggested acute appendicitis, and an open appendectomy was performed, revealing a tumor-like appendix without classic inflammatory changes. Histopathological examination revealed a moderately differentiated adenocarcinoma originating in the appendiceal mucosa with transmural infiltration extending to the serosa. Subsequently, a right hemicolectomy with D2 lymphadenectomy and ileotransverse anastomosis was performed laparoscopically, with a favorable postoperative course. This case highlights the diagnostic difficulty of appendix cancer and the importance of systematic histopathological analysis of appendectomy specimens.

KEYWORDS: Appendectomy, appendix, appendix cancer.

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INTRODUCTION

Appendiceal cancer represents less than 1% of all gastrointestinal neoplasms and is a rare and underdiagnosed entity. Its nonspecific clinical presentation, coupled with its low incidence, makes preoperative diagnosis difficult, so most cases are identified incidentally after an appendectomy performed for suspected acute appendicitis [1], [2], [3].

Among appendiceal tumors, adenocarcinoma is a rare subtype, but with a more aggressive biological behavior compared to well-differentiated neuroendocrine tumors [4], [5].

Clinically, these tumors can mimic common abdominal pathologies such as appendicitis, intestinal obstruction, or chronic abdominal pain, which delays diagnosis and definitive treatment [6], [7].

Surgical management depends on the histological type and the degree of tumor infiltration, with right hemicolectomy being the recommended treatment in cases of adenocarcinoma with transmural invasion or lymph node involvement [8], [9], [10].

The objective of this report is to describe a case of appendiceal adenocarcinoma diagnosed after appendectomy

and to discuss the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges associated with this entity [11], [12].

This retrospective case report study used data collected from medical records. Data confidentiality was maintained, and personal information was omitted, adhering to ethical guidelines for research involving human subjects. This study was deemed to have no risk. A literature review was also conducted using various databases, including articles published between 2020 and 2025, to inform the discussion of the topic.

CASE DESCRIPTION

A 58-year-old female patient, with no history of chronic degenerative diseases, reported smoking 10 cigarettes per day, and denied alcoholism or drug use, was admitted to the emergency department with a 3-week history of intermittent colicky abdominal pain, accompanied by nausea and constipation. She had been treated with multiple medications for these symptoms without improvement.

On physical examination, the abdomen was flat, soft, and depressible, with decreased peristalsis. It was predominantly tender to palpation in the right lower quadrant, and a palpable

Adenocarcinoma of the Appendix as an Incidental Finding after Appendectomy for Suspected Acute Appendicitis

mass was located in the same quadrant. Percussion was unremarkable. Laboratory studies were normal.

An abdominopelvic tomography (CT) scan with intravenous contrast was performed, which revealed an image in the right iliac fossa consistent with appendicitis (Figure 1, Figure 2).

FIGURE 1. Abdomino-pelvic axial CT scan with intravenous contrast: Image in the right iliac fossa, tubular, non-collapsed, and without air, with liquid density and pericecal changes, measuring 1.7 centimeters in its transverse axis and free fluid.

FIGURE 2. Abdomino-pelvic coronal section computed tomography.

A diagnosis of acute appendicitis was made, and an open appendectomy was performed. The appendix was found to be enlarged in its proximal third, with a tumor-like appearance, but without the classic macroscopic changes of acute appendicitis.

Histopathological examination revealed a moderately differentiated adenocarcinoma originating in the appendiceal mucosa and infiltrating the entire wall down to the serosa.

A right hemicolectomy with D2 lymphadenectomy and laparoscopic ileotransverse anastomosis was performed.

The patient was discharged six days post-surgery, with a good recovery and no complications.

DISCUSSION

Appendiceal cancer is a rare neoplasm of the gastrointestinal tract, characterized by a nonspecific clinical presentation and

a generally incidental diagnosis following appendectomy. The incidence of appendiceal cancer is estimated at 0.1 to 0.2 cases per million inhabitants per year, although this figure may be underestimated due to incidental diagnosis and misclassification as colorectal cancer [2], [5]. Population studies have shown a progressive increase in the detection of these neoplasms, probably related to the systematic histopathological analysis of appendectomy specimens [2], [6].

The average age at diagnosis is between the fifth and sixth decades of life, with variations depending on the histological subtype [1].

According to the World Health Organization, appendiceal tumors are mainly classified as well-differentiated neuroendocrine tumors, mucinous neoplasms, conventional adenocarcinomas, and goblet cell adenocarcinomas [7].

Neuroendocrine tumors are the most common and generally have an indolent course when they are small and localized [8]. Mucinous neoplasms, both low- and high-grade, are characterized by excessive mucin production and their potential for peritoneal dissemination, leading to pseudomyxoma peritonei [9], [10].

Appendiceal adenocarcinomas are usually diagnosed at advanced stages and exhibit a more aggressive behavior, with a worse prognosis [4], [11].

The pathophysiology of appendiceal cancer varies widely depending on the histological subtype. In mucinous neoplasms, appendiceal rupture and mucin release favor peritoneal seeding [10].

In recent years, genomic studies have demonstrated that appendiceal tumors have molecular profiles distinct from those of colorectal cancer. Alterations in genes such as *kras*, *gnas*, *tp53*, *smad4*, and *apc* are common, especially in adenocarcinomas and mucinous neoplasms [3], [12].

This genomic heterogeneity explains the differences in clinical behavior and therapeutic response, and opens new possibilities for targeted therapies [3], [12].

Most patients present with symptoms consistent with acute appendicitis, such as right lower quadrant pain, fever, and leukocytosis [1], [6].

In advanced stages, especially in mucinous tumors, abdominal distension, mucinous ascites, weight loss, and a palpable abdominal mass may be observed [9], [10].

Neuroendocrine tumors rarely produce carcinoid syndrome due to their early diagnosis and small size [8].

Preoperative diagnosis of appendiceal cancer is uncommon. Abdominal computed tomography is the imaging method of choice, allowing identification of appendiceal dilation, mucinous masses, or peritoneal implants [1], [6].

The definitive diagnosis is established by histopathological examination of the surgical specimen. In selected cases, tumor markers such as CEA, CA 19-9, and CA 125 may be useful for prognostic evaluation and follow-up [6], [11].

Treatment depends on the histological type, tumor size, local invasion, and presence of metastases.

Adenocarcinoma of the Appendix as an Incidental Finding after Appendectomy for Suspected Acute Appendicitis

Isolated appendectomy is sufficient for well-differentiated neuroendocrine tumors smaller than 2 cm without risk factors [8].

Right hemicolectomy is indicated in adenocarcinomas and mucinous neoplasms with mesoappendix invasion, compromised margins, or lymph node involvement [1], [4].

In patients with peritoneal dissemination, cytoreductive surgery combined with hyperthermic intraperitoneal chemotherapy (HIPEC) has been shown to improve survival in selected cases [6], [9], [10].

Systemic chemotherapy is reserved for advanced or metastatic disease [11].

The prognosis for appendiceal cancer is highly variable. Localized neuroendocrine tumors have five-year survival rates exceeding 90% [8].

Low-grade mucinous neoplasms have a favorable prognosis if complete cytoreduction is achieved, while high-grade adenocarcinomas and tumors with extensive peritoneal dissemination have worse survival [4], [5], [11].

Molecular classification is emerging as a promising tool for prognostic stratification [3], [12].

Appendiceal cancer is a rare, heterogeneous neoplasm with a complex diagnosis. Recent advances in pathology, oncological surgery, and genomics have led to a better understanding of its biology and improved therapeutic management. A multidisciplinary approach based on histological, molecular, and clinical criteria is essential to optimize the prognosis for these patients.

CONCLUSION

Appendiceal adenocarcinoma is a rare neoplasm that presents a significant diagnostic challenge due to its nonspecific clinical presentation and its similarity to common inflammatory processes such as acute appendicitis. Systematic histopathological examination of appendectomy specimens is essential for timely diagnosis. In cases with transmural infiltration, right hemicolectomy with lymphadenectomy is the treatment of choice and allows for accurate oncological staging. Clinical suspicion and appropriate surgical management are crucial for improving the prognosis of these patients.

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